

Roja - Recreating of Indian epics into

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Abstract

Literature and Movie combined together and have a powerful impact on those who wish to truly realized and understand what is meant by culture? The culture helps to study to learn, to experience, to feel and to know about past and present history of the country. The main impact of the Indian cinema was the cultural influences of the country. With this advent of cinema things were not the same and history was created. They gave India a global identity. In early days movies in India has been one of the keyways in which religion and mythology in particular has been mediated in India over the past centuries. The visual images creates more impact in the minds of the audience. So the writers must come forward and make their contributions available to the movies. Literature should break away from holier-than-thou attitude and approach cinema with the perspective of partnership. Only then both can grow. If it grown our culture uplift among all nations.

Introduction

More than 100 Years of Cinema Creates a Powerful impact in the minds of the audience. The main philosophy of the cinema is to entertain as well as to educate the spectators. Right from the Dadasaheb Phalke, father of Indian cinema till dated directors have a touch of Indian epics in their movies. Either as it the same or else they narrate the story in another way. For centuries we are tired of talking about Feminism, but there will be a big question mark regard this idea. Still the society needed stereotype women. If she walks out from this track means she will be labeled as negative character. For centuries this ideologies were reflected in movies also but now they changed their ideas towards women's, and the audience also accept it. In this paper I compare the movie Roja with “Ramayana” as well as “Mahabarata”.

Being a female reader I am so delighted to watch the movie Roja .I agree the view of the director. While watch the movie I can able to trace two female predominant characters from the epic “ Sita” and “ Savitari”.

The inspiration for th flim Roja was from the real life incident. This was taken up by the director and he transfred this incident to screan play and the letter which was sent by the real wife was the dialogue in the movie speak by the heroine with the terrorist.

Initially Roja does not like what Rishi because of his act, later she knew the truth from her sister and she starts to love her husband.

Here I trace the ways women can express their views in society in any circumstances, even choosing their grooms too. In Mahabratam 'Subhadra' she refused to marry Dhurodanan and she herself chosen her groom Arjuna as Shenbagam did in the movie. Heroine also at first refuse to accept him but later she understand her and love bloomed, and life is blissful for the couple for a short while. In the great Indian epic Ramayana 'Rama' and 'Sita' also faced many trouble after their marriage. They went for vanavasam for 14 years. Meanwhile, in the movie also due to Rishi's chief illness he takes up the responsibility and went to Kashmir here I trace the human ethics in all circumstances we have to obey our elders words. Both Rishi and Rama followed this.

Roja bravely tries to get help from politicians and the military to rescue her husband.. This incident found in the epic Mahabharata, While I go through Savithris story I came across a same experience. She went along with her husband to forest as like Roja went to Kashmir. When her husband was kidnapped she fights to rescue her husband. In Savithris story she fight with Yama and rescue her husband here she fight with the government and with the terrorist at last Bout the Female characters happily lead their life with their husband.

Roja have the traces of the legend character Savitry. Savarathi fights with Yama to rescue her husband soul here Roja rescue Rishi's life from the terrorist and finally lite Sathivan and savithri Roja and Rishi united once again.

In another way the Director breaks the stereotype of women. For centuries people accept the concept of Manu, that in no circumstances is she allowed to assert herself independently.

“Balya va.....” (Manu satram – 5/150)

A women are not allowed to work independently.

“Balye pitovashay.....” (Manu satram – 5/151)

Women always should depend on their father, husband, and hner son. They are not worthy to live independently.

In Ramayana Sita was kidnapped by king Ravana and he tries to seduced her but he frightened of Sita's chastity and he waited to convince her but this doesn't accept it and she made an oath that her husband surely rescue her likewise her husband also rescued him and killed king Ravana. But in the movie the heroine fights to rescue her husband and she succeed in it. Even though Sita is capable of rescue herself own but she waited for her husband to rescue her. She depended on her husband as like Manu Said. But in the Movie the director change the scene and he break out the stereotype the the heroine fought for her husband and rescue him from the terrorist.

I conclude this paper that the society is made up with so many ideas. Everybody is having different opinion towards it. If we need a change means we must have to change but this will not happened in a single day this will take place years to change but one day this society will definitely change its ideology towards women. The visual arts will always creates impact on audiences so the film makers take up the responsibility to teach ethics to the society.

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